

Basic Knowledge on DCCs

Information for Stakeholders

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DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.8199281

Content and goal

- These slides are intended as introductory material of Digital Calibration Certificate (DCC) for stakeholders of NMIs and DIs
- The purpose is to support the implementation of DCCs within the European metrology community
- The slides are part of a knowledge compendium also containing a common introduction to DCCs and more specific information for technical staff and management of NMIs and DIs

Stakeholders and benefits

Rapid growth of automation in combination with digitalization generates increasing need for measurement data. In Industry 4.0 scheme the measurement data, including the calibration information, flows through the whole production chain in digital format.

Stakeholders:

- End users in various fields, e.g. pharma, manufacturing and process industry
- Equipment manufacturers
- Calibration service providers
- Accredited laboratories
- Designated Institutes (DIs)
- National Metrology Institutes (NMI)

Benefits:

- Meet the customer needs
- Additional data analysis services based calibration meta data
- Reduced human errors
- Secure storage and easy access
- Cost savings in printing and storing paper certificates
- Reduction of waste and minimize the impact on the environment

Better use of calibration data enables

- **Data Analytics:**

By storing digital calibration data in a centralized database, it becomes possible to analyze the data to identify trends, patterns, and opportunities for improvement. For example, you can track the performance of a particular piece of equipment over time to determine if it is in need of more frequent calibration or if there are any underlying issues that need to be addressed.

- **Predictive Maintenance:**

By combining calibration data with other data sources, such as machine usage logs or performance metrics, it is possible to predict when equipment is likely to fail and schedule maintenance or calibration accordingly. This can help to minimize downtime and improve the overall efficiency of the equipment.

- **Improved Compliance:**

DCC helps organizations to demonstrate compliance with industry standards, such as ISO 9001 or ISO 17025.

- **Enhanced Customer Service:**

By making digital calibration data readily available to customers, organizations can provide a higher level of service and support. For example, customers can access their calibration certificates and data at any time, without having to wait for the organization to retrieve it.

- **Improved Decision Making:**

By having access to up-to-date and accurate digital calibration data, organizations can make better-informed decisions about their equipment, such as when to replace equipment, allocate resources, or make other critical decisions.

Business canvas for stakeholders

Western Europe was the third largest region in the measuring and control instruments market worth \$137.9 billion in 2020, accounting for 19.6 % of the global measuring and control instruments market, preceded and followed by North America at 27.7 % and Eastern Europe at 5.6 % respectively. The Western Europe measuring and control instruments market is expected to grow to \$188.59 billion by 2025.*

Problem

Traditional paper calibration certificates are often misplaced or damaged, making it difficult to prove that the equipment is accurately calibrated. Handling and storing the paper copies of calibration certificates is slow, expensive and prone to errors. Receiving DCCs e.g. through email is possible for a small number of calibration providers, but receiving DCCs from hundreds of different calibration providers needs to be highly organized and automated.

Solution

A digital calibration certificate platform that allows companies to easily access and store calibration certificates in a secure online portal.

Value proposition

- Simplified record keeping in a central, online location, making it easy to track and manage calibration. This task could be also outsourced to a service provider.
- The platform enables additional data services, ensures that calibration certificates are up-to-date and accurate, reduce the risk of errors in equipment readings.
- Time and cost savings by automating the calibration certificate process.

*Measuring and Control Instruments Market covering Other Electrical Equipment, Electronic Products And Components; Navigational, Measuring, Electro medical And Control Instruments; Global Summary 2021

Status of DCC development and use

According to the DCC2GO questionnaire performed spring 2023, 15 % of the respondents are already DCC ready and about 34 % will be ready next year. One third has no implementation schedule at the moment.

The number of publications related to DCC has increased rapidly during the last years. They report DCC requirements, conceptual studies, specific application implementations, security, and small scale implementations.

Internet trusted sites provide open access tools, examples and guidance for DCC implementation. Information is available from conferences and DCC development committees.

Regulatory requirements

- The existing legal and regulatory requirements for calibration certificates apply to DCCs as well
- DCC can fulfil the existing requirements and fully replace the non-digital calibration certificate

An easy introduction of DCCs could be based on having a conventional analogue certificate, that is already fulfilling all legal and regulatory requirements, accompanied by a DCC.

Standardization of DCCs

Why standardization is needed?

Automated data handing and machine readability requires increased standardization of data formats in order to remove possible misinterpretation

What needs to be standardized?

- **Common formats** for providing calibration data in digital and machine-readable form
 - Common provision of content of first page (administrative data)
 - Unambiguous and clear representation of measurement data, methods, equipment, terminology, etc.
- **Measurand-specific representation of the calibration data**
 - It needs to be made very clear which information must be provided for each measurand
 - Standardization starts with an refinement of the existing analogue standards

What is the status of standardization?

- Today, harmonization of DCC formats are driven by NMIs and industry. Several organizations have created committees to assess and progress the development and implementation of DCCs

Example of DCC implementation

A DCC Proof-of-Concept DCC was successfully developed and tested over the whole calibration traceability chain. The DCC generation tool in Vaisala and the DCC receiving in Orion's CMS were implemented as a part of the organizations' existing information technology environment. Other components of the infrastructure were implemented as a part of a cloud-based data transfer platform. At each step, the DCC includes all necessary information for traceability e.g., measurement data, deviation, uncertainty, and measurement references.

Ref. Juho Nummiluikki, et.al, DEVELOPING AND TESTING DIGITAL CALIBRATION CERTIFICATE IN AN INDUSTRIAL APPLICATION, IMEKO TC6 International Conference on Metrology and Digital Transformation 2022, Berlin, Germany

Role and development per partner

Partner	Role in the project	Development action in the project
Aalto University	Aalto University was the project coordinator and developed the data transfer platform and cloud components for DCC management	The data transfer platform created by Aalto enabled system-to-system integration of different Calibration Management Systems (CMS) of each partner eliminating the need for e.g., emails as a transfer method.
VTT MIKES	VTT MIKES is the National Metrology Institute (NMI) in Finland and provided the expertise of calibration certificates and traceability to the project.	Calibration certificate generation in MIKES is based on proprietary in-house software together with Microsoft Office tools. In this project a manual DCC creation tool was used, but soon after MIKES developed a middleware to convert calibration result excels automatically to DCC
Beamex	Beamex, an integrated calibration solution provider, was the calibration management system specialist and developer in the present project.	DCC import to the CMS was tested as a part of the Beamex CMX environment to enable automated import of calibration results from the DCC.
Vaisala	Vaisala is the manufacturer of the instrument used in the calibration containing humidity and temperature sensors. They operated as an accredited calibration service provider and a DCC receiving party. They both received a DCC from MIKES and sent a DCC to Orion	The certificate creation process at Vaisala was already highly digitalized within Vaisala's calibration management platform, hence automated DCC generation was possible to test due to fully machine-readable data.
Orion	Pharmaceutical company Orion was the other DCC receiving party and the endpoint of the calibration chain.	The DCC created by Vaisala was received by the calibration end user Orion. Orion uses a commercial off-the-shelf calibration management system, Beamex CMX.

Summary of the project

1. Development of the DCC PoC was implemented step-by-step

- First a DCC was manually created using existing PDF certificates as a template and delivered manually
- In the second phase the receiving party used the DCC to import calibration results to their CMS followed by semi-automated end-to-end testing
- Finally, interoperability of all the DCC generation and reading methods were tested with each other

2. Software components were developed and test independently using as much commercial services as possible

- A signature validation service was used as a part of the data transfer platform
- Human readable format of DCC was developed using XSLT and JavaScript technologies
- DCC data parser was developed to enable fully automated and error resistant data transfer process for the customer CMS
- DCC sharing was implemented through a data transfer platform used by all the partners in the project. The data privacy of each organization was achieved through multitenancy.
- The user management in the tested solution was based on Microsoft Azure Active Directory (AAD)
- DCC storage was not included in this project

3. Lessons learned

- The solution presented in this PoC was considered effective and user friendly for DCC exchange
- The cloud-based platform offered a low entry level for organizations with less software development capabilities
- As use case specific needs and data formats can vary, there needs to standardize the data in a more detail level

How to tackle the challenges of DCC

Topic	Challenge	Solution
Technical	How to cope with different data systems and non-standard interfaces?	Examples and good practice models can be found e.g. from www.ptb.de/dcc . Adopt widely accepted industry standards and promote their use across stakeholders.
	How to handle large data volumes and maintain optimal performance?	Employ scalable architecture and infrastructure to accommodate increasing data and user loads. Utilize cloud-based services, auto-scaling mechanisms, and load balancing techniques.
	How to ensure data security and privacy from unauthorized access or manipulation?	Implement robust encryption techniques, access controls, and authentication mechanisms to safeguard the data. Regular security audits, vulnerability assessments, and staff training should be conducted.
Management	Change management	Information of DCC is available in internet trusted sites and scientific conferences. Learn from experience of pierce. Coordinate and align multiple stakeholders with diverse interests and priorities when planning the transition.
	Investment in data infrastructure and personnel?	Implementation of DCC requires investments in financial, human, and technological resources, but in the long run, the automation of calibration process will bring cost savings to the organization.
	Schedule of DCC implementation of and standardization?	The implementation of DCC has already started in NMIs and industry despite of the lack of standardization. Early adaptors will lead the development of DCC.

Various other aspects of DCCs

- Machine-readability and cross-domain interoperability of DCCs
- Secure transmission of DCCs across European borders and to countries outside Europe
- DCCs in the context of quality management and accreditation
- Access to open access software and good practice examples
- Guidance to legal requirements and standardization
- Ability to participate in and contribute to committees who develop DCCs

Please visit the following presentations for details

Common
introduction to DCC

DCC
for
Management

DCC
for
Technical Experts

Credits

21SCP01 DCC2GO

Supporting the implementation of Digital Calibration Certificates in the European metrology community

April 2022 – September 2023
Coordinator Anke Keidel (PTB)

E-mail
Webpage

dcc2go@ptb.de
<http://www.ptb.de/dcc2go>